

Study of Clinical Profile (Types and Grade) of Anemia in Antenatal Patients

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Abstract:

Anemia in pregnancy is one of the most common ailments affecting mothers worldwide. The condition has been estimated to affect around a quarter of the global population, with the majority of women being from the developing countries of Southeast Asia, including India. Anemia in pregnancy is caused by a multitude of factors. Of them, the most important is the increase in the demand for iron and other vitamins in the body. Populations of developing countries such as India have an already high burden of nutritional deficiencies, of which one of the most prevalent is iron deficiency.

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Introduction

Anemia in pregnancy is one of the most common ailments affecting mothers worldwide. The condition has been estimated to affect around a quarter of the global population, with the majority of women being from the developing countries of Southeast Asia, including India. Anemia in pregnancy is caused by a multitude of factors. Of them, the most important is the increase in the demand for iron and other vitamins in the body. Populations of developing countries such as India have an already high burden of nutritional deficiencies, of which one of the most prevalent is iron deficiency.

Maternal complications found to be associated with anemia in pregnancy include conditions such as antepartum and postpartum hemorrhages, pre-eclampsia, puerperal sepsis and thromboembolism. In the fetus, these complications include premature birth, low birth weight, and increased risk of fetal distress, and long-term physiological and psychological impairments after birth.

Research on the topic suggests that the prevalence of anemia in pregnancy among Indian women is much higher than the global prevalence. Therefore, regular assessment of the prevalence of the clinical profiles of anemia in pregnancy and its associated maternal and fetal outcomes in different sub-populations is required.

In this context, the present study was planned to assess the type and severity of anemia in antenatal patients presenting to the department of Obstetrics and Gynecology of a referral hospital in Delhi, India.

Aims and Objectives: The aim of the present study was to study the clinical profile (types and grades) of anemia in antenatal patients presenting to the department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, NRCH, Delhi.

Objectives: The primary objective of the present study was to find clinical profile (types and grades) of anemia in antenatal patients at NRCH.

The secondary objective of the present study was to find the association of maternal and fetal outcome with types and grades of anemia in antenatal patients at NRCH.

Materials and Methods

Study Setting: The study was conducted at the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology of the Northern Railways Central Hospital, New Delhi, India.

Study Duration: The study was conducted for 8 months, from May 2023 to December of 2023.

Study Design: The current study was an institution-based observational study with a prospective design.

Study sample and grouping method: The study population consisted of antenatal women with singleton pregnancies presenting to the study institution during the period of study and diagnosed with anemia as per the WHO criteria (hemoglobin level <11 g/dL).

Inclusion Criteria: The inclusion criteria for the study population were:

1. All antenatal patients with singleton pregnancy attending the department of Obstetrics and Gynecology of NRCH, Delhi
2. Women with hemoglobin level of <11 g/dL
3. Women with a gestational age of ≥ 12 completed weeks

Exclusion Criteria

The exclusion criteria for the participants that were considered for the current study were as follows

1. Women who refused to provide written informed consent to take part in the present study
2. Women aged <18 years
3. Women with multiple pregnancy
4. Known case of anemia before pregnancy
5. Known case of chronic medical illness
6. Suffering from bleeding disorders in the current pregnancy.

Method of Selection

A consecutive sampling technique was used to recruit patients in the study. Pregnant women presenting to the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology of the study institution during the period of the study and diagnosed with anemia were evaluated for the present study.

Data Collection: All pregnant women fulfilling the inclusion criteria and ready to give written valid informed consent were included in the study. Based on pre-designed questionnaire, data were recorded for the study. All pregnant women coming to outpatient department were advised for blood test (CBC) at her 1st antenatal visit.

The second testing was done during 16-20 weeks. The third testing done during 30-34 weeks. As a part of the blood examination, venous blood sample 5 ml were collected in EDTA vacuette. After collecting the blood, they were transferred into a properly labelled vacuette. This vacuette was then used for analyzing various hematological parameters (Hb, RBC count, HCT, MCV, MCH, MCHC & RDW) with the help of automated hematology analyzer. Patients with diagnosed anemia were managed as per hospital protocol of the management of anemia in pregnancy. As per the World Health Organization, the severity of anemia was classified as:

Table 1:

Severity	Hemoglobin level
Mild	9 – 10.9 g/Dl
Moderate	7 – 8.9 g/dL
Severe	4 – 7 g/dL
Very severe	<4 g/dL

In the patients a peripheral blood smear was made to study the type of anemia as normocytic normochromic, microcytic hypochromic, macrocytic or dimorphic anemia. Serum folic acid, Serum B12, Iron studies (serum iron, ferritin, unsaturated iron-binding capacity (UIBC), total iron-binding capacity (TIBC), and percent saturation of transferrin) were also be done to rule out the underlying cause of anemia. HPLC was done to identify Thalassemia. The patients were followed up till their delivery, and the maternal and fetal outcomes were evaluated during antepartum, intrapartum, and postpartum period:

Maternal outcome: Preterm labor, PPH, failed lactation, Infection, postpartum pyrexia

Fetal outcome: Premature baby, Low birth weight, IUGR, IUD, Low APGAR score, NICU admission.

Sample Size: Laspal et al. observed that iron deficiency anemia has the highest prevalence

(71.47%) followed by megaloblastic anemia (18.23%) and dimorphic anemia (6.2%), and hemoglobinopathies (4.1%) respectively. Furthermore, when the authors assessed the severity of anemia, they found that 35% patients had mild anemia, 44.7% had moderate anemia and 20.3% had severe anemia.

Taking this value as reference, the minimum required sample size with 10% margin of error and 5% level of significance is 95 patients. To reduce margin of error, total sample size taken is 100.

The sample size was calculated as per the Cochran's formula:

$$N \geq Z_{1-\alpha/2}^2 * (p * (1 - p)) / (ME)^2$$

Where Z_{α} is value of Z (normal variate) at two-sided alpha error of 5%, ME is margin of error and p is prevalence of iron deficiency anemia, megaloblastic anemia, dimorphic anemia or

hemoglobinopathies and proportion of patients with various grade of anemia. The sample size was 100.

Ethical Consideration: The Institutional Ethics Committee of NRCH, Delhi reviewed and approved the project before it was carried out.

Results

Most participants were between 25 and 29 years old. Hindus were the most numerous. 66% of the patients were from urban residences. As per the modified Kuppaswamy scale, majority of the participants were from middle-class families and had completed their secondary school level of education. The prevalence of illiteracy was 11%. 20% of the women were primigravida, and the rest were multigravida. It was observed that of the women, most had moderate grade of anemia (43%). 15% of the women had severe anemia. The commonest reported symptom of anemia was weakness (52%). The commonest morphological diagnoses were microcytic hypochromic anemia (57%), and the commonest clinical diagnosis was iron deficiency anemia (57%), followed by β Thalassemia trait (19%), and folic acid deficiency anemia respectively (12%).

Regarding maternal adverse outcomes, the incidences of preterm labor, PROM, LSCS delivery, maternal infection, maternal ICU admission and maternal deaths were 38%, 45%, 35%, 16%, 9%, and 0% respectively. There was a statistically significant association between the incidence of maternal complications such as preterm labor, PROM, maternal infection, PPH and maternal ICU admission with the severity of anemia among them. Similarly, the incidence of adverse fetal and neonatal outcomes such as IUGR, VLBW, LBW, APGAR of <7 at 1 min, NICU admission, and neonatal death were 19%, 20%, 45%, 19%, 35%, and 8% respectively. There was also a statistically significant association between the incidence of intrauterine growth restriction, low birth weight, APGAR <7 at 1 min of birth, rates of NICU admission and neonatal death with the severity of anemia among them.

Discussion and Conclusion

The present study observed that among mothers presenting to the study institution with a hemoglobin concentration of <11 gm%, the most common age group was 25-29 years, with multi- and grand-multipara mothers being the most affected. 15% of the women had severe anemia, with microcytic hypochromic being the commonest morphological diagnosis and iron deficiency being the most common clinical diagnosis. Of the 100 women studied, 19 were positive for β Thalassemia trait. The observations made in the present study also shows that there was a high incidence of adverse maternal and fetal outcomes among the women. Maternal morbidities such as preterm

labor, PROM, LSCS delivery, and maternal infection were commonly encountered. Similarly, high proportions of the neonates suffered from complications such as IUGR, VLBW, LBW, APGAR of <7 at 1 min, and NICU admission.

On statistical analysis, it was observed that there was a statistically significant association between the incidence of fetomaternal morbidities and severity of maternal anemia.

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